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ADOPTION OF ELECTRIC VEHICLES IN LOGISTICS: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: An electric vehicle (EV) is an automobile powered by electricity stored in batteries instead of traditional petrol or diesel. One of the key differences between electric and conventional vehicles lies in their charging systems. Today, electric cars are seen as one of the major innovations to reduce air pollution, mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, and promote environmental sustainability and clean air. Additionally, EVs contribute to decreasing global dependence on oil, a valuable and finite natural resource. As the cost of fossil fuels continues to rise, electric vehicles present significant economic advantages for national economies.

This thesis explores the adoption of electric vehicles and examines both the challenges and opportunities associated with their integration into Uzbekistan's logistics sector. It begins with an overview of logistics and a brief introduction to electric vehicle technology, followed by an analysis of the benefits and barriers to EV implementation. Furthermore, it discusses how EVs can improve transportation service systems. The ultimate goal of this research is to support the widespread adoption of electric vehicles in Uzbekistan's logistics industry, stimulate domestic production, and promote public interest in eco-friendly transportation alternatives.

Key words: electric vehicles, drones, automotive industry, hybrid cars, air pollution, fossil fuels, greenhouse gas effects, collaborative systems, foreign practices.

Annotatsiya: Elektr avtomobili — bu an'anaviy benzin yoki dizel yoqilg'isi o'rniga batareyalar orqali harakatlanadigan transport vositasi bo'lib, ularning eng katta farqlaridan biri zaryadlash tizimidadir. Bugungi kunda elektr avtomobillari havo ifloslanishini kamaytirish, issiqxona gazlari chiqindilarini qisqartirish va ekologik barqarorlikni ta'minlash yo'lida eng samarali yechimlardan biri sifatida qaralmoqda. Shuningdek, ular insoniyatning qimmatli va tugab borayotgan tabiiy boylik — neftga bo'lgan ehtiyojini kamaytirishga xizmat qiladi. Neft va boshqa qazilma yoqilg'ilarning narxi kundan-kunga oshib borayotgani sababli, elektr avtomobillari mamlakat iqtisodiyoti uchun muhim afzalliklarga ega.

Mazkur ilmiy ishda O'zbekistonda elektr avtomobillarni logistika tizimiga joriy etishning imkoniyatlari va muammolari tahlil qilinadi. Dastlab logistikaga oid umumiy tushunchalar va elektr transport vositalariga oid qisqacha ma'lumot beriladi, so'ngra ularning joriy etilishiga to'sqinlik qiluvchi va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi omillar ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, elektr avtomobillarining transport xizmatlarini takomillashtirishdagi roli ham muhokama qilinadi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi — O'zbekiston logistika tizimida elektr avtomobillarini ommaviy joriy etish, ularning mahalliy ishlab chiqarilishini rag'batlantirish hamda aholi orasida ekologik toza transportga qiziqishni oshirishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: elektr avtomobillar, dronlar, avtomobil sanoati, gibrid mashinalar, havo ifloslanishi, qazilma yoqilg'ilar, issiqxona effekti, hamkorlik tizimi, xorijiy tajribalar.

Аннотация: Электромобиль — это транспортное средство, работающее на электричестве, аккумулируемом в батареях, вместо традиционного бензина или дизеля. Одним из ключевых отличий электромобилей от обычных автомобилей является система зарядки. В настоящее время электромобили рассматриваются как одно из наиболее значимых открытий в борьбе с загрязнением воздуха и парниковыми газами, а также в обеспечении экологической устойчивости и чистого воздуха. Кроме того, они способствуют снижению зависимости от нефти — ценного и ограниченного природного ресурса. С учетом постоянного роста цен на нефть и ископаемое топливо электромобили приобретают экономическую значимость для национальных экономик.

В данной работе рассматривается внедрение электромобилей в логистическую систему Узбекистана, а также анализируются основные проблемы и перспективы их применения. Исследование начинается с краткого обзора логистики и технологий электротранспорта, после чего подробно анализируются возможности и препятствия на пути их внедрения. Также обсуждается, как электромобили могут повысить эффективность транспортных услуг. Основной целью исследования является содействие широкому внедрению электромобилей в логистику Узбекистана, развитие их местного производства и повышение интереса населения к экологически чистому транспорту.

Ключевые слова: электромобили, дроны, автомобильная промышленность, гибридные автомобили, загрязнение воздуха, ископаемое топливо, парниковые газы, системы сотрудничества, зарубежный опыт.

INTRODUCTION

The worldwide issue towards sustainable transportation systems has become a crucial priority for policy-makers, companies, and environmental supporters. A highly promising solution is the use of electric vehicles, providing a more environmentally friendly and energy-efficient option compared to conventional fossil powered transport. In the logistics industry, adopting electric vehicles can greatly decrease carbon emissions, reduce operational expenses, and improve supply chain efficiency. Nonetheless, although the uptake of electric vehicles has accelerated in various regions globally, incorporating them into logistics processes offers distinct opportunities and challenges. Uzbekistan, a swiftly advancing nation in Central Asia, is presently facing a pivotal moment regarding its transportation and environmental strategies. The logistics industry in Uzbekistan is vital for linking the nation to regional and global markets, but it heavily depends on traditional internal combustion engine vehicles. The nation encounters an increasing need for more sustainable and economical transportation options, making the embrace of electric vehicles in logistics both a practical and essential move for its future progress.

Nowadays electric vehicle is one of the most popular type of transportation both in logistics and also in environment. At first electric cars were appeared in the early XIX centuries nonetheless, in our current times they are much more developing and be common in use. Electric vehicles are considered one of the most eco-friendly vehicles because they do not harm ecology with their carbon dioxides (CO₂). Even though electric vehicles, hybrid vehicles or drones are more expansive than traditional cars, the demand of the public is getting more higher day by day. On the one hand, electric vehicles are beneficial for ecology as they do not produce carbon emissions and prevent air pollution.

Opportunities of electric vehicles in Uzbekistan's logistics

There are a number of opportunities are recommended by adoption of electric vehicles particularly, in Uzbekistan's logistics which is increasing economy and modernization. As global concerns, attraction of governments should be intended in ecology because the environment is not sustainable even getting worse. That's why, the main issue is getting electrification so one of them is changing road transportation. It is interesting that, why only road transportation because it is possible to install extra battery tank to airplanes or ships however, recharging system is a bit more challengeable. So that, the most suitable way is road transportation even more in passenger vehicles. In Uzbekistan opportunities of electric vehicles are so wide firstly, as mentioned before our atmosphere is getting polluted day by day by several items like main by industries, factories, green gas effects and carbon dioxide. One of the results is electric vehicles which they do not harm to environment and do not produce carbon emissions. Another possible side is electric vehicles can prevent of increasing cost of fossil fuels and natural oil. Because of high demand in oil in order to use as petrol or diesel in decades the cost of oil is very high. Even though, oil is our natural treasure we should save it and utilize in different spheres which get more benefit rather than used as petrol. As electric cars powered with batteries it is very crucial to take extra battery power in a long distance rather than building a big charging stations on the way in order to placing new buildings. Battery powered cars very efficient and affordable to charging for drivers however, the cost of the car is a bit more expansive than traditional cars. As last-mile delivery system or on-demand delivery is a bit more expansive to people while they used expansive petrol or diesel so if it would be battery used car it will increase the number of delivery service and online trading in Uzbekistan.

Challenges of electric cars in logistics of Uzbekistan.

Accurately, for new customers and countries adaption of electric vehicles prompt several discomforts and take a time to adopt. Even though in Uzbekistan the utilizing of electric vehicles appeared several times before but still people have some kind of unsure ideas about them, for instance, they are worry about running out of battery especially, in long term distance. Because in Uzbekistan lack of recharging station and battery spares in addition, ordinary public do not adapt to work with high technics. As we know electric vehicles are included very expensive spare parts and specifically, battery is still costly for public and this is the main issue of customers who want to buy electric vehicle. Another reason is a seasonality of electric vehicle in case of working not so well during winter season people are getting more worried about being without machine during cold weather in addition, as soon as it will be cold the batteries waste more power and it will be cause of reduction of long distance. Recently, it proved that recycling system of batteries are not enhancing yet so also electric vehicles harm to ecology by this way. On the top of that, everywhere of Uzbekistan is not equality in electric voltage for example, in suburb areas we can face with a low quality of light. Additionally, it more depends on seasonality because during winter some people also suffer from low quality of energy who lives in rural areas. That's

because when it needs to charge battery of electric car in a long distance several times it may cause to reduce the life of batteries. Specifically, to cut down the disadvantages of electric vehicles in Uzbekistan, government should supply a better quality of energy light and develop infrastructure. Furthermore, producing a whole car can cause more ecologic problems rather than their zero emissions while driving so, to contribute a whole industry of making electric car in Uzbekistan will be face with high problem which harm all generation with polluting a soft air. Infrastructure of electric vehicle need wide area where any people do not live however, in our country this kind of place are not appropriated to this condition.

Using new methods from abroad as model for adopting electric vehicles in Uzbekistan.

Clearly, infrastructure of electric vehicles has been changed rapidly in a last decades. They are not only eco-friendly transport view, but also the future representation of transport in case of reducing need of energy and carbon emissions. Electric vehicles used for different needs of public in abroad such as: as a private transport, for business and social services and also for delivering goods. First aid of them makes short distance trips efficiently, reduce the cost and protect the environment. Technological innovations, improvements in battery systems, and the development of electric vehicles charging infrastructure are playing an important role in the production and expansion of electric vehicles. In this research new methods of foreign countries analyzed and make new models in Uzbekistan's logistics systems to. For instance, in a sample of Norway, Sweden, Northern Ireland, China and Germany. There are a number of incentives introduced by Sweden to enhance the affordability and appeal of EVs for consumers. the encompasses tax cuts, rebates for buying electric cars and waivers from tolls and parking charges. The Swedish government provides subsidies for setting up home charging stations, enhancing the convenience of owning an EV. Numerous Swedish firms are offering EV charging facilities at their workplaces, motivating staff to use electric vehicles. In certain instances, companies are providing subsidies or incentives for workers to purchase EVs, thereby enhancing the shift towards more eco-friendly transportation alternatives. Swedish cities, such as Stockholm, are establishing low-emission areas where entry is restricted to electric vehicles or hybrid cars. These areas are included in initiatives aimed at lowering air pollution in urban centers, and they promote the shift towards cleaner, more sustainable vehicles for people and companies. As in Uzbekistan there are a number of problems which people suffer from lack of recharging station and it will be improved if that kind of models used also in Uzbekistan to encourage population's interest. For example, free charging fields only for minutes front of markets or political companies or make green zones like gardens parks let to entering only electric cars. These methods will be the best strategy for encouraging and supporting EVs owners and others to contributing the future of Uzbekistan logistics by getting change of traditional transport into electric cars.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical background

Originally developed in 19th century, electric vehicles are automobiles that run entirely on electricity. However, they were not intended for general public use. Electric vehicles are regarded as one of the most practical and beneficial types for all needs following a number of scientific studies and activities. Battery-powered vehicles are utilized worldwide for a variety of applications, including shipping, and delivery services. Although they are mostly employed for public transit in this instance, there are also potential benefits for Uzbekistan's logistics industry. In this field of the subject many more scientists and researchers have worked already and give some samples bellow related to their work. In this part the purpose of my thesis is to explore more objectives of electric vehicles and get new samples and bring to bear of new fields and innovations in Uzbekistan too.

Relevant studies

First and foremost, it is important to find out a better direction to adopting electric vehicles in every society for this reason many researches outlined a number of strategies and one of them is given, for example, Yuanzhi Wang, Frank Witlox find out that, rather than having a unified strategy for all electric cars, rules should be established for each type of technology independently. Determining the psychological, social, economic, environmental and technical factors that influence the choice of electric vehicles can help states and the auto industry increase the percentage of people who drive electric vehicles (Yuanzhi Wang, Frank Witlox, 2025). The adoption of electric vehicles has been encouraged worldwide for the advantages that EVs are anticipated to provide regarding energy security, global and local surroundings, and economic development. Energy safety could be enhanced as battery electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles decrease the oil usage of nations customarily depending significantly on overseas imports. Effects on worldwide the impact of climate change from the transportation sector can be minimized if the roadway the electrification of transport takes

place simultaneously with the decarbonization of energy production. Local air contamination, particularly in city regions, can be lessened as a greater proportion of driven miles is handled by zero tailpipe vehicles with low emissions like battery electric vehicles. Economic development can be encouraged through the establishment of a supply chain for EV production along with installation of the charging infrastructure and the creation of company to run it (Nicolò Daina, Aruna Sivakumar, John W.Polak, 2016). Numerous advantages including lower noise pollution and exhaust emissions, the use of electric vehicles for private passenger transportation in urban areas is having a growing positive influence on our environment and society (Niklas T., Tan Y., Kenal D., Alexander P., 2024). Generally, transportation has a significance impacts on political and economic sides of Uzbekistan clearly, as looking deeply to annual GDP nine percent of Uzbekistan's GDP is derived from the transportation sector. Especially, road transport, which can offer door-to-door services and is the most crucial means of mobility for both freight and public transit, is primarily responsible for this contribution (Yakhshilikov J., Marco Cavana and Pierluigi Leone, 2024). The Uzbek government has implemented a number of measures to lessen the carbon footprint of the transportation sector in order to address the environmental and public health issues related to emissions from this industry. Over the past ten years, CO₂ emissions from Uzbekistan's transportation industry have steadily increased. The sector's emissions increased by an average of 5% per year between 2010 and 2020, mostly due to an increase in road freight transportation and car ownership. The biggest sources of transportation emissions are freight trucks and passenger automobiles, both of which mostly run on gasoline and diesel (Khamdamov, 2024).

Since the development of electric vehicle infrastructure necessitates the opening of new markets for cutting-edge goods, it requires the active support of numerous governmental social and industrial sectors. Additionally, it is essential to continuously assess the trends and status of the global and Uzbek electric car markets (Umerov F.Sh., Asanaov S.E., 2023). Further researches in this issue of future of transportation in Uzbekistan analyze that, in order to populace with a modern effective, and environmentally, friendly transportation system, Uzbekistan's automotive transportation industry must strike a balance between economic growth and environmental sustainability (Tilavqabilova D., Bakhromov F, 2024).

European countries plan implemented several plans in order to the future of transportation among eight European towns, the FREVUE initiative showcases the application of electric freight vehicles (EFV) in city logistics operations. The European Commission is providing co-funding for the project through the Seventh Framework Program (Hans Quak, Nina Nesterova, Tariq van Rooijen, 2016). Initially, Norwegians begins to change road transportation to EVs because of the goal that, to protect the atmosphere from transportation disaster that's why used electromobility system and could deserve their aim. Incentives for utilizing EVs can also yield a beneficial impact regarding emissions of greenhouse gases. Taking into account the CO₂ emissions by vehicle category times the price of CO₂ per ton released in accordance with the Norwegian Handbook for impact assessment, the benefits of transitioning from a traditional vehicle to an EV can be obtained (Marie Aarestrup Aasness, James Odeck, 2015). Additionally, private automobiles are responsible for around 12% of global greenhouse gas emissions. Overall, the transportation industry is responsible for around 22% of greenhouse gas emissions (Moataz Mohamed, Chris Higgins , 2016).

Currently, electric transports are much more popular it is clear that, not only road transports will be popularized but also rail road transport changing into autonomic sample because of innovations. However, nowadays many countries could not apply due to the energy consumption also in case of Uzbekistan this problem didn't solved yet. By three incentives such as promotion of electric vehicles, expansions of infrastructure and research development could focus on decarbonization sector of transport (Yakhshilikov J., Marco Cavana and Pierluigi Leone, 2024)

Meanwhile, during researches Uzbek researchers explore the advantages of electric vehicles in city logistics, including decreased environmental impact and improved cost efficiency, while also tackling issues such as inadequate infrastructure and the need for technological adjustment. Their research revealed that embracing EVs might lower operating expenses for logistics firms over time, especially regarding fuel savings and upkeep (Saidova F., Hamroyev A., 2025).

METHODOLOGY

Especially, in this thesis used secondary data, survey and interview in order to identify more realistic answers and ideas. Survey was filled by 25 respondents and their answers are given in detail. Moreover, interview was taken by 3 foreigners which took place in Registan square. They were given three different questions revealed to adoption of electric vehicles in their countries.

Figure 1: SWOT diagram

Table 1. SWOT ANALYSIS

<p>STRENGTH Environmental benefits Technological advancements Developed public image Government support Eco-friendly vehicle</p>	<p>WEAKNESS High initial costs Lack of charging stations Lack of skilled workforce Lack of spare parts in exported countries.</p>
<p>OPPORTUNITIES Improved export and import Economic diversification Make more modernized High demand for sustainable energy Create more services and jobs</p>	<p>THREATS Environmental impact of battery High risks to change Economic factors Competition from established fossil fuel vehicles</p>

This method can help to clarify more clearly, as main issues of research is given here for taking consideration each factors of electric vehicles. There are several opportunities and strengths to using in a case of developing green logistics systems with ecofriendly cars, despite of them a few weaknesses and threats of electric vehicles on environment and economy. However, government take into consideration such kind of problems and trying to developed and will change transportation infrastructure.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

According to participants' answers I can say that public are ready to buy an electric version of transportation on the one hand, if government cuts down some tariffs and others mean that how laws will be broken and it depend on them like incentives, regulations and so on. I think it is a bit elevating because by this tariffs and laws government could imports and exports and it is very significant to economy of Uzbekistan. On the other hand, the electricity is considered a big border for functions of electric vehicles. Interestingly, people even thought that kind of views like if government should ban of selling a non-battery car then people would must buy modern version of vehicles. It is also a new method would be.

Overall, people enumerate several challenges which come across with electric vehicles such as, more than half of respondents are worry about high cost, lack of charging points, and not having of companies which produce spare parts of electric vehicles because our country has been work collaboratively with others

1 Source: own elaboration

countries. However, others options are quite different for instance, not an equal electricity voltage in everywhere of Uzbekistan and could not urge to equal providing of high valued electricity. Besides, options are not only the lack of factory, but also the need of electronic vehicles constructor. In addition, some people said the limited range of imported vehicles can cause to less service for example, they need a small version of electric vehicles only delivery system for limited distance and then it would be change in logistics. Moreover, lacks of recycling system in Uzbekistan and weaknesses of supply chain of batteries that's why, opportunities for labor partnership with other countries as masterclass for our native mechanics. In some cases, people think that the weather also could be cause to reduce the lifetime of batteries as winter affects to driving range.

DISCUSSION

According to provided questions French tourist answered that, as France main energy and electricity come by wind power and nuclear. So, the public think that, after several years if many more usages of electric vehicles and others electronic technics, the need of electricity will be high and governments may be could not supply with energy. That's why in France may be apply the crisis of electricity so nations are a bit more worry about it.

Moreover, other participant who came from UK, asked by another question which was about the condition of electric vehicles and in which service would you suggest electric cars? The answer was when she travelled with electric cars problem was with its air conditioning and sometimes it didn't work well or almost did not switch on because of its battery. She said if drivers switch on air conditioner the battery life will be reduced and could not work much more. So that, she sees more electric cars in delivery system services but not in order to a taxi in UK. Of course, her suggestion will be work well in economy of country.

The last participants from USA who lives in a rural area of America his answer was about challenges of electric vehicles according to his mind driving an electric vehicle will be challengeable because around near of his house there is no any charging stations of electric vehicles and people are suffer from lack of stations when they drive to longer destinations. He said that government should support suburb areas also with the latest facilities, then it will be better to use electric cars in logistics. According to their answer's conclusion is in different parts of the world are still developing in this sphere so that, the percentage of advantages and disadvantages is equal, the more advantages people apply, the more challenges will come.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the adoption of electric vehicles in Uzbek logistics provide a number of opportunities for modern businesses and in a global environment. Some of these issues common with electric vehicles which they do not harm to environment and do not produce carbon emissions. Even though there are a number of harms which impact on ecology to getting worse of air in city center greenhouse gases are significant role to harm to air because of other companies, firms and fabrics situated in rural places. Another possible side is electric vehicles can prevent of increasing cost of fossil fuels and natural oil. In decades the cost of oil is very high because of high demand in oil using as petrol or diesel. Besides, getting modernization in transportation system produce high decorated and brand cars on the street means that wealthy population as well as wealthy environment. On the other hand, estimated several challenges of electric vehicles as mentioned before electric vehicles are included very expensive spare parts and specifically, battery is still costly for public and this is the main issue of customers who want to buy electric vehicle. Another reason is a seasonality of electric vehicle in case of working not so well during winter season people are getting more worried about being without machine during cold weather in addition, as soon as it will be cold the batteries waste more power and it will be cause of reduction of long distance. Moreover, the quality of battery related to working ages of it because in a normal using one battery can work well in eight years maybe because there are several factors which could impact on battery one of them is recharging with not original components. So, it can be cause to reduce quality main part of car.

In my view, although shifting the electric vehicles in logistics in Uzbekistan will require time, it both attainable and essential for the sustainable development of the nation, success hinges on a joint endeavor involving the government, industry and stakeholders, and global partners to tackle the financial and infrastructure obstacles. By making appropriate investments and implementing effective policies, Uzbekistan has the potential to become a leader in green logistics within Central Asia.

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